

An Assessment on Proliferation and Implications of Central Mosques for Friday Weekly Prayers in Bauchi Metropolis, Bauchi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Bauchi emirate was founded by one of the disciples of Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī Mallam yā'qub ibn Dādi. Mosques being one of the symbols of religion and one of the most important institutions in any Islamic state were among other things established by Amir Yā'qub at some strategic places with a Central one in front of his palace. The mosque remained the only Juma'at mosque in the town for decades. However, in the late 20th and early 21st century, Bauchi started experiencing rapid proliferation of Juma'at mosques. This paper attempts to examine the trend of the proliferation of Juma'at mosques in Bauchi town and its implications using historical methods, primary and secondary sources, oral interviews, archival materials and other extant literature. The paper discovered that constant and sustained increases in population, urbanization, competition and contestation for the religious public sphere by the various Islamic groups and philanthropic activities of some wealthy Muslims, politicians and Government patronage are among the factors that lead to these phenomena. The paper finally recommends among other things the need for the regulation of the establishment of Friday mosque by the constituted authorities in conjunction with other religious bodies and organizations for the cohesion and harmony of the Muslim Ummah.

Keywords: Proliferation, Bauchi Emirate, Friday Mosque,

Introduction

Masjid is an Arabic word, which is simply translated to mean Mosque. A mosque is a building where Muslims worship (Hornby, 2022). The mosque, according to Abdul Fattah (2007) is the house or a

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specified place where Allah is worshipped. while (Yahaya, 2020) is of the view that a Masjid (Mosque) aisa place specially consecrated for all acts of sincere worship and submission to Allah which includes teaching and learning of religious studies and activities of preaching (*Da'awah*) and reconciliation of disputes or rifts.

The importance of Mosque in Islam is so paramount that different verses of the Glorious Qur'an epitomize its usage by all Muslims' For example, as a cardinal importance to remember Allah therein, the Noble Qur'an states:

وَمَنْ أَظْلَمُ مِمَّنْ مَنَعَ مَسْجِدَ اللَّهِ أَنْ يُذَكَّرَ فِيهَا اسْمُهُ وَسَعَىٰ فِي خَرَابِهَا ۗ أُولَٰئِكَ مَا كَانَ لَهُمْ أَنْ يَدْخُلُوهَا إِلَّا خَائِفِينَ ۗ لَهُمْ فِي الدُّنْيَا خِزْيٌ وَلَهُمْ فِي الْآخِرَةِ عَذَابٌ عَظِيمٌ

And who is more unjust than he who prevents (men) from the Mosques of Allah, that His name should be remembered in them, and strives to ruin them? (As for) these, it was not proper for them that they should have entered them except in fear; they shall meet with disgrace in this world, and they shall have great chastisement in the hereafter (Q2:114).

The above verse according to Yahaya (2000) establishes the fact that Mosque in Islam has its origin. The first Mosque to be established was the Masjid al-Haram (Ka'bah) in Makkah as established in the Glorious Qur'an, Allah (SWT) says:

إِنَّ أَوَّلَ بَيْتٍ وَّضِعَ لِلنَّاسِ لَلَّذِي بِبَكَّةَ ۗ مُبْرَكًا ۗ وَهُوَ الَّذِي لِلْعَالَمِينَ ﴿٩٦﴾

Most surely, the first House (of worship) established for mankind is the one of Bakkah [i.e.; Makkah] blessed and guidance for the (entire) world Prophet (3:96).

Building or establishing of mosque is one of the paramount duties of every capable Muslim individual or community, as they are told that they would earn huge rewards from Allah not only in this world but also in the hereafter. Prophet Muhammad is reported to have said:

“Whoever builds a mosque for Allah, Allah would build similar to it for him in paradise”(Muslim Book of Masajid Hadith Number 1218)

Another Hadīth on the authority of Usman bin Affān goes thus:

“Whosoever builds a mosque where Allah's name is being mentioned Allah would build a house for him in paradise (Sunan Ibn Majah Kitabul Masajid wal jama'ah Hadith No. 735)

Mosques throughout the history of Islam have been solid institutions serving multiple functions that are not confined or restricted to spiritual matters alone. The roles of Mosques among Muslims extend to other socio-economic and political spectrums such as education, zakat collection and distribution charity and almsgiving, political mobilization, etc. In recognition of the important role of mosques among the Muslims, the Sokoto Jihad leaders used to emphasize the erection and maintenance of mosques in the appointment letters to the new Emirs appointed. Mallam *yā'qubu* ibn Dādi one of the disciples of Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī, and the founder of Bauchi Emirate like other flag bearers was given a formal letter of investiture as the first Amir of Bauchi by Sheikh Uthmān bin Fūdī and the letter among other things states “...I command you to exert yourselves in repairing and maintaining mosques.....(Yero (1999).

The first mosque built by Mallam *yā'qubu* was in Inkil town before the establishment of Bauchi town. However, with the establishment of Bauchi town, about twelve mosques were established at some strategic locations with a Central one in front of the Emir's palace which remained the only Juma'at mosque where the people of Bauchi metropolis and its environs trooped weekly to observe Friday prayers with Mallam Yaqub as the first Imam (Yero,1999). However, around 1820 perhaps due to the

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pressing and persistent task of running the emirate, Mallam *yā'qubu* had to appoint somebody to take over the office of the Imam in person of Mallam Bahago son of Mallam Adamu Maudo. (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, 11th March 2018).

Since the time of Amīr Yaqūb, the institution of mosques in the Bauchi emirate has been under the office of the Chief Imam of Bauchi who supervises and regulates its establishment. No new mosque can be established except with the consent and approval of the Emir who sends the chief Imam or his representative to conduct prayers in the mosque as a mark of the Emir's approval. (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, 23rd November 2023).

The precedence set by Mallam *yā'qubu* where the emirate had a serious stake in the establishment and coordination of mosques and appointment of Imams remained in force over the centuries even after the colonisation of Northern Nigeria by British Emperors.

This according to (Abubakar 2021) greatly assisted in maintaining unity among the Muslim *Ummah* in the emirate.

This development, however, was to suffer some setbacks, especially from the 1980s due to many reasons culminating in the proliferation of Juma'at mosque in Bauchi Metropolis with its attendant consequences. This paper, therefore, traces the history of the establishment of the Friday mosque in Bauchi, the role of the Bauchi Emirate in this regard and the proliferation of mosques experienced since the 1980s.

Islam in Bauchi Emirate

Before the 19th century *Jihād* of Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī, the region out of which the present Bauchi emirate was carved, was a predominantly pagan area (Sulaiman 1987 and Yero 1999). Islam was said to have been introduced to the Bauchi region from Borno and Hausa land as far back as before the 18th century through trading activities between the Muslim traders from Borno and the non-Muslim people residing in the region and the missionary activities of some Islamic scholars. One such Scholar was Mallam Ishāq who hailed from Borno and moved to Ganjuwa and later Jitar town. Coincidentally, it was this scholar who served as *yā'qubu*'s first teacher and the one who took him and introduced him to Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī in Sokoto. This according to Umar (2016) has confirmed that there was Islam in the region only that its impact was negligible because its spread was considerably slow.

When Mallam Yaqūbu was commissioned as the flag bearer of the Bauchi region he was reinforced with learned scholars by Shaykh Uthmān bin Fūdī and charged with the command of waging a *Jihād* upon the Bauchi pagans. Yaqūbu was said to have first settled in Inkil town for about four to eight years before establishing Bauchi town where he engaged in the mass calling and conversion of the pagans to Islam through various means including sending his envoys to the leaders of the various pagan communities (Yero 1999). According to Sulaimān (1997), Mallam Yā'qubu embarked on extensive resettlement schemes aimed at boosting Muslim populations, providing defences for them as well as improving agriculture. The overall result was the emergence of new towns with absolute Muslim majorities serving at the same time as urban centres in the Bauchi emirate. These centers were in line with the overall Sokoto caliphate *Ribat* Policy which served as military garrisons against any possible attack on the territory and helped significantly in promoting mass literacy, urbanization, socialization food production and security throughout the caliphate. New towns such as Kafin Dulumi, Kafin Madaki, Rauta,

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Nasarawa, etc. were all established by the Bauchi emirate for this purpose. (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, 23rd November 2023).

Bauchi Emirate and the establishment of Friday Mosques

One important impetus to the growth of Islam in the Bauchi emirate was the way the area came to be proliferated with ranks of scholars over the years. Mallam Yaqūbu, in compliance with advice offered to him by Sultan Bello in his popular treatise, *Al-Ghayth al-Shu`ub fi Tawsiyati Amir Ya`qub*, was said to have recruited a considerable number of scholars with requisite qualifications who served in various capacities as scribes, special advisers or officials attached to the administration of justice, while others served as imams of mosques and disseminators of Islamic education. (Zailani N.D). He was said to have surrounded himself with the company scholars whom he consulted in almost every affair of state (Ado Dan Rimi, personal interview, May 3, 2018).

In compliance with the terms of his appointment, as mentioned earlier, Yaqūbu was said to have constructed Mosques in almost all the places he succeeded in bringing under his suzerainty. In Bauchi, the capital of the emirate for instance, about twelve mosques are said to have been strategically established at different locations plus a Central one in front of the Emir's palace. Whenever there is a vacancy in the office of the Imam it is the emir that has the sole right and responsibility to appoint a new one from among the learned scholars of the town after consultations with his council and after a careful assessment (Umar 2016).

The first person appointed as Imam of the Bauchi Central Mosque was Mallam Bahago son of Mallam Adamu Maudo next after him was Mallam Jibrilla, then Mallam Nurudeen son of Alqādi Mallam Qāsim, next was Imam Ahmadu, then Imam Muhammadu, then Imam Mahmood, then Imam Ahmad Bāban Inna son of Imam Mahmood, after him Imam Muhammad Inuwa Jahun then Imam Bala Ahmad who is the current chief Imam. (Ado Danrimi, personal interview, May 2018)

Since the time of 'Amīr Yaqūbu, the institution of mosques in the Bauchi emirate has been under the office of the Chief Imam of Bauchi who supervises and regulates its establishment. No new mosque could be established except with the consent and approval of the Emir who sends the chief Imam or his representative to conduct prayers in the mosque as a mark of the Emir's approval. This had been the system in the Bauchi emirate for decades until the early eighties (B. Baban Innah, personal interview, May 3, 2012).

Proliferation of Juma'at Mosques in Bauchi Metropolis

From the late 80s and early 90s to the present time, there has been a constant and massive proliferation of Juma'at mosques in the Bauchi metropolis a phenomenon which according to Cleo Cantone (2012) was not peculiar to Nigeria. Many factors have been identified as the brain behind these phenomena some of which include;

1. Emergence of the Izālah Movement

One of the factors that led to the proliferation of Mosques in the Bauchi emirate is the emergence and activities of the Izālah movement or organization and the uncomplimentary and hostile attitude exhibited by the emirate council to the movement. Described by Lomier (1997), as one of the most influential and powerful reform movements in northern Nigeria, Formed by some Muslims in northern Nigeria to preach and uphold what they believe to be the correct doctrines, teachings and practices of Islam as enunciated in the Qur'an and the prophetic traditions.

The *Izālah* members in particular give preference to the building of their mosques because it serves as a centre for the dissimulation of their mission. When they decided to open their own separate

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Juma'at Mosque in Bauchi in 1978, they wrote a letter to the Emir of Bauchi through the then Chief Imam late Ahmad Mahmood Bāban Innah informing the emirate council of their intention. After inviting them for a discussion, the Emirate Council rejected their move based on the reason that the move would divide and foment trouble among the Muslim Ummah. (M. Gidado Umar, personal interview, May 3, 2013).

However, in defiance of the emirate council's order, the Izālah movement went ahead with their plan by opening their first Juma'at Mosque in Bauchi town in Gwallaga quarters in 1978, thus eroding for the first time the power of the emirate council of approving the establishment of Friday mosque. The Emirate Council on its part wrote a letter to the Nigerian Police seeking for the closure of the Mosque for fear of possible unrest. Consequently, the Mosque was closed down by the Police and the designated Chief Imam Mallam Gidado Umar and some other leaders of the organization were arrested and detained in police custody and later taken to court for prosecution. However, they were eventually acquitted and set free by the court.

The treatment meted out to the members of the *izālah* movement by the Emirate council which culminated in the court judgment in their favour made them perceive the Emirate council as being unsympathetic to their course as such they embarked on the establishment of more mosques in different locations throughout the Emirate without seeking approval of the Emirate Council. Some of these mosques include the Bākin Kura Mosque built by the Late Alhaji Abdullahi Mai Auduga at Bākin Kura quarters (which was later expanded and upgraded to Juma'at Mosque) and the Bukar N.T.C. Mosque built by the late Alhaji Bukar Birma at Bākaro quarters and several others. As the number of mosques kept on increasing the Izālah organization had to create a special directorate saddled with the task of regulation and co-ordination of the Mosques under its control, especially the Juma'at Mosque. This is a sharp contrast to the Mosques that are under the control of the Emirate councils

In 1991, a dispute which is seen by many as due to leadership tussle within the leadership of the movement erupted which led to the split of the movement into two factions. The dispute according to Lomier (1997) acquired a rather bitter note because of the stubborn adherence of both factions to doctrinal arguments leading to the mutual accusation of *kufr* and *shirks* by each side to discredit the other side. Just as the *Izālah* movement discouraged their followers from praying behind the Sufi or in the mosque's control, so also the warring *izālah* factions issued verdicts discouraging or even prohibiting their followers from praying behind their rival factions. A clear example is contained in a pamphlet titled: "*Hujjojin da suka hana bin wadanda suke bin Sheikh Isma'ila Idris Sallah daga Alkur'ani da hadisi*" (i.e "pieces of evidence from the Qur'an and Hadith against praying behind the supporters of Shaykh Isma'ila Idris" (written by one Umar Muhammad Nasarawa Sābon Pegi, Adamawa state, Nigeria and endorsed by the Adamawa state Chairman Council of Preachers under the Kaduna faction of the Izālah. (Gurama, 1999).

As each faction wants to dominate the religious space against the other faction, there emerges a new trend of a multiplicity of both Juma'at and five daily mosques in many communities in the Bauchi metropolis. There are instances where multiple Juma'at or five daily prayer mosques are cited within a particular vicinity where there is a need for only one. For instance, in the Kandahar quarter, it is estimated that there are not less than fifteen Juma'at and over twenty daily prayer mosques belonging to two different *izālah* factions. In the same Kandahar quarters there are two Juma'at mosques very

close to each other and belonging to two different *izālah* factions. Along Gombe Road and Bauchi Central Car Park all in the Bauchi metropolis, there are two Mosques located opposite to each other. According to Baban Innah (B. Baban Innah, personal interview, May 3, 2012), the number of mosques under the jurisdiction of the *Izālah* organization in Bauchi and its environs put together might outnumber those that are under the control of other Islamic organizations. This is a sharp contrast to the mid-seventies were there were only one Juma'at mosque in Bauchi.

2. Population explosion and rapid urbanization

The constant and sustained population explosion coupled with rapid urbanization in the late eighties and early nineties in Bauchi led to the expansion of existing settlements and the emergence of new ones, especially outside the walled city of Bauchi. The primary factor responsible for this is the uncontrolled migration of people from rural areas and the neighbouring states. In 1991 and 2004 for instance, Plateau state experienced one of the bloodiest ethnic-religious crises that claimed hundreds of lives and rendered thousands of people homeless. There was also the Boko Haram crisis which ravaged Borno and some parts of Yobe state these fracas led many people to migrate to the neighboring Bauchi state which was closer in terms of proximity, especially Bauchi town and its environs for their safety. This phenomenon led to the emergence of new settlements in Baran Kandahar quarters, Bayan Airport quarters and a couple of others that are located outside the traditional Bauchi walled town, these provided opportunities especially for different Muslim groups to build new Friday and five daily prayer mosques in each of these new settlements.

3. Investment in Mosque building by some wealthy businessmen and politicians

Investment in the building of Mosques is one of the paramount duties that attract great rewards. Prophet (S.A. W.) was reported to have said

Whoever builds a masjid (mosque) for the sake of Allah,
Allah will build something similar for him in Paradise. (ibn
Majah Chapter hadith no.735)

The above quoted and similar hadith might have been one of the reasons that prompted Muslims, especially the well, to embark on the building mosque. In Bauchi metropolitan city as discussed earlier, the first Juma'at mosque owned by the *izālah* movement was a house donated by Alhaji Sule Makanike, which was converted to Juma'at Mosque.

There was also the Late Alhaji Audu Mai Auduga, who built a Juma'at mosque for the *izālah* at Bākin Kura quarters, The Abu-Huraira Juma'at mosque, built by the Late Alhaji Nuru Jibrin, the late Alhaji Ishaqa Jibrin who built a Juma'at Mosque along Ran Road in Bauchi. Engineer Zubairu Ya'qub built a Juma'at Mosque at the G.R.A. behind Bauchi State Government House, Bauchi.

Besides these there are also some politicians and other government functionaries who built Juma'at mosques among them is; Mallam Isah Yuguda the former Governor of Bauchi state who built Umar bin Khattab Juma'at mosque at Rafin Albasa Quarters in Bauchi, the former Minister of the Federal Capital Territory and present governor of Bauchi state senator Bala A. Muhammad who built Uthmān bin Fodio Juma'at Mosque at G.R.A. also in Bauchi metropolis. Most of these mosques are handed over to the Islamic organizations to which the donors subscribe.

4. Official Government patronage

Official patronage by the government is another factor that aided the proliferation of Jum at mosques in Bauchi. There are some mosques such as the Kasuwar Shanu Juma'at Mosque, the Abdurrahman bin Auwf Juma'at Mosque at Zango quarters, the Ibrahim Bako housing estate Juma'at mosque and

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the Mallam Mai Tauhidi Juma'at mosque along Atiku Abubakar way and many more which were constructed by the Bauchi State government between 2021 and 2023 thus increasing the number of Friday Mosques in Bauchi Metropolis.

5. Donations from International Islamic organizations

These organizations provided funds for the purchase of land and the construction of mosques in both the rural and urban areas of Bauchi. For instance, two mosques and Islamic centres were built by the Revival of the Islamic Heritage Society Kuwait and donated to the Jamā'atu izālatil bid'ah in 2017. There is also *Ikhlās* Mosque built by the Mu'assatul Tanwiril Islamiy in 2018. There is also the Masjid Salmānul Fārisy for the *Jama'atu Tajdidil Islam* in Inkil built by an international charity organization and many others.

6. Competitions among Muslim organization's

As mentioned earlier, the Jama'atu *Izālatil Bid'ah* organization gives preference to the building of a mosque which serves as the mobilization and propagation centre of their activities. Their defiance of the emirate council's directives as mentioned earlier had instigated other groups to follow suit. The Tijjaniya Muslim Brotherhood for the first time built their separate Juma'at mosque in 2008, at Makera quarters in Bauchi. The Jamā'atu Tajdidul Islam (J.T.I.) have their Juma'at Mosque in Inkil, the As'hābul Kahafi Warraqimi built their Friday Masjid in Kandahar Quarter, the Nasrullahil Fatih (NASFAT) have their own along Maiduguri road by Firo, the Ansārudeen Muslim Society have their own along Kofar wase road and many more.

Summary and Conclusion

Mosque has been an important Islamic institution in Bauchi from the time when Islam was consolidated up to the 21st century. The centrality and significance of the Juma'at Mosque make the traditional authority in Bauchi oversee all the religious activities that take place within it. The First Juma'at Mosque was located in front of the Emir's palace to effectively control the congregants and imams. Whenever a new mosque was to be established, it was within the customary jurisdiction of the Emirate council to approve; this has been the practice from the time of the First Amir Mallam Yakubu up to the post-colonial period.

Although the unsympathetic and hostile attitude of the Bauchi emirate council towards the *Izalah* movement led them to establish their mosque formation of the *Izālah* movement in the late 70s and early 80'80s other factors such as demographic change, rapid urbanization, and the emergence of new settlements as a result of ethno religious crisis in some neighbouring states, competition among other religious groups, patronage from Government, Politicians and other well to do have all contributed into the massive building of Juma'at mosques in every nook and crannies of Bauchi Metropolitan and its environs. The results of all these translated into the massive proliferation of Juma'at mosques and thereupon the massive fragmentation of the Muslim Ummah along doctrinal lines which jettisoned the customary power of the Emirate Council concerning the establishment of new mosques and went ahead to build their separate Juma'at mosques.

Recommendations

This paper wishes to make the following recommendations

- i. There is a need for the government in liaison with the Emirate Council, local government authorities and Muslim Organizations to form a forum or set a guideline for the regulation

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- and establishment of Mosques especially the Juma'at Mosque by various organizations for cohesion and harmony of the Muslim *Ummah*.
- ii. The emirate council's old tradition of regulating and guiding the establishment of Juma'at Mosques by each Muslim organization should be restored by the Government which should in liaising with representatives of all Muslim organizations set guidelines for the establishment of Friday Mosques.
 - iii. The unguided freedoms of religion brought by democracy whereby politicians engage in the building of Mosques also need to be controlled by the government.

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